

Method and algorithm for calculation of ordinary and turbulent flows in an incompressible fluid

Theses

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1. The author proved the existence of a unique solution of the Navier-Stokes equations for a viscous incompressible and compressible fluids - see “Navier-Stokes equations. On the existence and the search method for global solutions. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1307808>

2. A method is also proposed for the search for this solution, which consists in moving along the gradient to the unique saddle point of some functional. It should be noted the complexity software implementation for its.

3. For a viscous incompressible fluid, a simple method for finding a solution is proposed, consisting in moving along a gradient to a single point of a convex functional.

4. An algorithm for such a search is also proposed. In this algorithm, we use a scalar parameter whose magnitude affects both the accuracy of the solution found and the rate of convergence. More precisely, with increasing accuracy, the decision time also increases. Accuracy can be arbitrarily high. The criterion for completing the search is the fulfillment of the power balance condition: is zero the sum of

- a. the power of mass forces,
- b. the power of the change in energy loss by internal friction,
- c. the power of changing the energy flow through a given volume of liquid, which is equal to the sum
- d. the power of the change in energy with a change in the flow direction and
- e. the power of changing the operation of pressures.

5. For the stationary case, experimental programs have been developed in the MATLAB system realizing this algorithm. A detailed consideration

- a. flow in mixers of various designs,
- b. flow in the annular tube,
- c. flow in an infinitely long tube,
- d. flow in a pipe with obstacle,
- e. flow in a pipe with variable mass forces.

6. An explanation is proposed for the mechanism of the appearance of turbulent flows, which is based on the Maxwell-like equations of gravitation, refined on the basis of known experiments - see "Gravitomagnetism: Nature's Phenomenas, Experiments, Mathematical Models." DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1308670>

7. It is shown that the source of turbulent forces is the gravitomagnetic interaction of moving fluid molecules. This, in particular, explains the spontaneous transition from laminar flow to turbulent flow with increasing flow velocity.

8. The calculation of turbulent forces as function of the flow velocity and a certain physical parameter of the liquid, called the turbulent density, is given. It is shown that it depends on the size of the molecules, the density of the liquid, and the gravitational constant. The velocity function, which is part of the definition of turbulent force, is called a turbulean. Thus, the turbulent force is the product of turbulent density and turbulean.

9. From the foregoing it follows that the turbulent force can be considered by analogy with the product of the mass force on the density of the liquid (this product enters the Navier-Stokes equation). Therefore, the turbulent force enters as another term in the Navier-Stokes equation. We call such augmented equation the Navier-Stokes equation with turbulence.

10. A method for solving the Navier-Stokes equations with turbulence is proposed.

11. An algorithm for implementing this method is also proposed, similar to the algorithm described in § 4. In this algorithm, the criterion for ending the search is also the fulfillment of the power balance condition, which additionally takes into account the power of the turbulent forces.

12. For the stationary case, experimental programs have been developed in the MATLAB system realizing this algorithm.

13. It is shown that the energy of turbulent forces is converted into energy of heating and work of pressures - **turbulence raises temperature and pressure**. It is known that there are devices in which this additional energy created by turbulent forces is used - so-called cavitation heat generators. At present, there are many such devices that differ in the ways of creating turbulent motion. Such devices provide efficient, simple, inexpensive and reliable sources of heated water and other liquids for domestic and industrial use. Together with the existence of such heat generators there is no generally accepted theory that reveals the source of additional energy that appears as a result of the operation of these cavitation heat generators. There are other devices that demonstrate the existence of an inexplicable increase in energy, for example, Rank's tube, Kotousov's nozzle.

14. It is shown that the source of turbulent forces is the gravitational field of the Earth. The application of the proposed method for calculating turbulent flows allows us to perform the optimal design of above-mentioned devices.

15. The author seeks assistance in continuing work in this direction. Such assistance can be

- a. the participation of independent researchers and students interested in this topic,
- b. inclusion of this topic in the university plan,
- c. start-up firm,
- d. search for grants,
- e. receiving a Prize from the Clay Mathematics Institute; this institution called the solution of the Navier-Stokes equations one of the seven problems of the millennium, for which a prize was assigned – see http://www.claymath.org/millennium/Navier-Stokes_Equations/